

D5.1

Scalable and Adjustable Documentation of How to Understand the Aggregators' Technical Requirements

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Authors	Arnaud Gingold (https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0466-5542), Nathan Cuel-Oller (https://orcid.org/0009-0004-2310-6657)
Abstract	The report presents the first version of the CRAFT-OA T5.1 deliverable aiming at providing to the Diamond publishers a documentation about academic indexing services. It contains a description of an index knowledge base and a series of synthetic documentation about major indexing services.

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List of Acronyms

AHCI	Arts & Humanities Citation Index
APC	Article Processing Charges
API	Application Programming Interface
BASE	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine
CEEOL	Central and Eastern European Online Library
CORE	Connecting Repositories
CRIS	Current Research Information Systems
CSAB	Content Selection and Advisory Board
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DoA	Description of Action
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EDM	Europeana Data Model
e-ISSN	Electronic International Standard Serial Number
EU	European Union

HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
IPSP	Institutional Publishers and Service Providers
IS4OA	Infrastructure Services for Open Access
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
JASPER	Journals are Preserved Forever
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KB	Knowledge Base
MARC	Machine-Readable Cataloging
NLM	National Library of Medicine
NPP	Non-profit Partnership
OA	Open Access
OADJ	Open Access Diamond Journal
OAI-PMH	Open Archive Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPERAS RI	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PDF	Portable Document Format

PII	Personally Identifiable Information
PLACE	Publishers Learning and Community Exchange
PMC	PubMed Central
PMID	PubMed-ID
REST	Representational State Transfer
ROAD	Directory of Open Access scholarly Resources
RoMEO	Rights Metadata for Open Archiving
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SCIE	Science Citation Index Expanded
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SHERPA	Research Preservation and Access
SSCI	Social Sciences Citation Index
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
T	Task
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

VDR	Visibility, Discoverability, and Recognition
WoS	Web of Science
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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APPROVAL PENDING

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Task (T) 5.1 of the CRAFT-OA project addresses the topic of the academic publications indexing from the point of view of the publishers, especially the Open Access Diamond Journals (OADJs). OADJs do not always match the requirements of the main indexing services, either because of their own technical capacities, or because of the biases of the indexes. The task's objective is to help OADJs to know more about the indexes' requirements and to better understand the global landscape of academic publications indexing. The main output of the task will be a synthetic documentation about a large set of indexing services, containing structured and comparable information, alongside useful links to more in-depth technical documentation. In this way, the T5.1 documentation will help OADJs to improve both their knowledge of technical requirements and their awareness of all the indexing possibilities for their contents. In particular, the documentation will bring a clearer identification of the different types of services concretely operating academic publications indexing (e.g., search engines, catalogs, directories, etc.). Furthermore, the extensive documentation will describe the indexing services based not only on prestige criteria, but also, for instance, on interoperability, additional services, or bibliodiversity criteria. In order to build the documentation, the T5.1 started with the analysis of existing academic indexes lists to extract useful analytical categories. This work resulted in a Knowledge Base (KB) about a first series of indexes, using an identical structure for all the indexes. This set of organized information served then as a source for the creation of the documentation itself. The documentation aims at presenting the information stored in the KB in a more user-friendly and explicit way, corresponding to either explanation of the KB content, or selection within this content. The current work represents a first version of the documentation, which will be refined and finalized until the end of the project. The documentation, and potentially the KB, are meant to be integrated in the Living handbook that is being currently developed by CRAFT-OA Work Package (WP) 7.

2 PREPARATORY WORK: PUBLICATIONS' INDEXES STATE-OF-THE-ART

2.1 Getting Visible: The Diamond Publisher's Perspective

The task 5.1 addresses a specific component of the academic publishing landscape: the discovery channels and their requirements. While these channels are often described from the point of view of the end-user, with a profusion of lists about the “best” search engines and catalogs, or from the point of view of the service, with an assessment of its quality or impact, it is less common to read about what is required from publishers to be visible in these discovery tools, except for the most used ones, and even less to find a synthetic view of the landscape. However, even if not exhaustive, a description of these channels and of their requirements is particularly important for Open Access Diamond Journals (OADJ) and their publishers. On one hand, some of the most important referencing services are built around a very specific type of publishers, defined, even if tacitly, by their disciplines, publication's language, geographical provenance, and industrial resources, a typology which precisely does not correspond to the majority of diamond publishers. On the other hand, diamond publishers, being most of the time small teams focusing firstly on the scientific quality of the publications, often lack either the technical skills, or the technical support, or more simply the time, to dive into all the referencing services' specifications and even more to fully address them. Therefore, it seems useful to provide this community with some tools to better understand the context and its challenges.

With such an objective, the task intends to answer to the challenges identified in the project proposal:

- challenge domain I “Technical state of the art of journal platforms and technical processes”: the task will indeed give “access to approved information of, expertise about, and tools for Diamond OA publishing”¹;
- challenge domain III “Visibility, Discoverability, and Recognition (VDR) for Diamond OA IPSP [Institutional Publishers and Service Providers] and their content”: the task “will gather knowledge to find promising pathways for proper indexing”².

More precisely, in complement to the improvement of OADJs' expertise in publishing best practices and standards through guidelines and training developed especially in Work Package (WP) 3, the task intends to provide the publishers with a comprehensive view and a clearer understanding of the indexes landscape, where these best practices and standards can concretely be applied. Within the WP5, the task's output is also closely connected to T5.2 “Visibility pathfinder”, and will be useful to inform the building of the Diamond Discovery Hub

¹ See CRAFT-OA Consortium (2022). *CRAFT-OA Proposal*. Proposal number: 101094397. Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01. Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-02. Submitted 20.04.2022. Section “1.2 How the project goes beyond the State of the Art”. Part B. p. 8.

² See CRAFT-OA Consortium (2022). *CRAFT-OA Proposal*. Part B. p. 9.

(DDH) in T5.3 by providing descriptions of a wide range of indexes, and giving therefore the possibility to assess the potential reuse of the DDH data by third-parties.

The task intends to guide OADJs on the path from visibility to discoverability by bringing to them awareness and knowledge about a variety of discovery channels. It is not in the scope of the task to give a detailed step-by-step documentation about submission processes or standardization requirements for each indexing service, but rather give a synthetic overview containing the most important information, together with the appropriate links, that will help OADJs to compare the indexing services and evaluate which ones are the most useful for their own case. In that sense, it provides a foundation on which T5.2 will be built, as the aim of this task is to categorise the requirements of different indexes and to provide a tool for journal editors to navigate the indexing landscape, as well as an incentive for them to increase the visibility of their journals by joining various indexes and aggregators. It also complements the DDH, which will make OADJs metadata available for the indexing services to retrieve. The T5.1 will more broadly give a structured overview of a variety of indexing services and display, from the point of view of the content producers, i.e. the publishers, their types, operations, specificities, limitations, and benefits. Like other outputs of the project, it will support the OADJs in their effort to ensure their visibility, in a first stage, and then, in a more advanced stage, their discoverability.

While the two terms are often used interchangeably, visibility and discoverability actually differ³. In the digital context, “visibility” mostly refers to the verifiable presence of an item on the internet, and therefore mostly to its compliance with the global, and minimal, requirements of this technical system. The notion of visibility is often used in a marketing perspective, with merely commercial objectives focusing on proprietary services, but also, and perhaps more importantly, it implies a low compliance degree which actually limits the connection with the overall environment. A simple hyperlink to the Portable Document Format (PDF) of a publication is technically visible on the internet, but without the appropriate connectors, it is not fully discoverable, and its visibility might even remain a pure potentiality. “Discoverability” refers indeed to the possibility to actually find a resource in the mass of visible resources thanks to its capacity to answer to a query, from a human or a machine. Discoverability can be reached through an improved interoperability of the content obtained by rich and standard metadata, persistent identifiers for the publication and the authors, controlled vocabularies for the keywords, etc. All these features provide additional connectors to the publication and ensure their discoverability by enabling them to respond to a greater number of more complex and precise queries. This has a strategic value for OADJs, as they often struggle to be referenced by some of the more prestigious indexing services, and it is also for them an important criteria in assessing the quality of the indexing services, as the same prestigious services are not necessarily the most interoperable.

Notwithstanding, the T5.1 does not only focus on the technical dimension, as some of the indexing services dedicated to academic publications also have requirements concerning the editorial quality. In fact, some of the most important indexing services, like Web of Science (WoS), Scopus or Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), have a submission process that entails a very detailed and demanding assessment of the journals' scientific quality and

³ *Ibid.*

production regularity. Without duplicating these services' own documentation on their admission process, it is precisely in the scope of the T5.1 to provide the OADJs with a documentation that will help them to evaluate which kind of requirements, technical or editorial, minimum or optional, they will have to match to be referenced on each indexing service.

2.2 Overview of the Publications Indexing Services

The indexes for academic publications present a specific challenge for OADJs which does not depend in the first place on skills or knowledge about the indexes, but on the actual complexity of the landscape. A quick look at a list on Wikipedia⁴ shows not only that there is a great amount of such indexes or that their types and requirements can differ a lot, but also that there appears to be a limited number of truly comparable aspects. Indeed, while the Wikipedia list can compare the access cost and the access to the data, the features of the services are all listed in one box which does not allow for a detailed comparison. It is therefore necessary, in a first stage, to identify what hinders and what allows an accurate comparison.

First of all, it is not accurate to present the global landscape of scientific publications' indexes as a uniform set of interchangeable services, a sort of supermarket where a consumer would freely choose generic products on a, yet limited, but partially rational basis. The choice is in great part oriented by contextual factors, which often determine the level of knowledge publishers can have about the various indexes. Practically, the indexes do not share the same strategic value, and this value is often for the publishers the first reason to look for, or care about, a specific index. In many cases, funding agencies or research evaluation processes consider the indexing on major proprietary platforms as an efficient, if not the only criteria to evaluate research activities' impact. Therefore, publishers trying to increase their visibility according to such criteria only take into consideration a few indexes, although their admission process can be demanding and not always successful. A strategic value can however also be reached by an index thanks to its specific vision and quality (e.g., DOAJ specifically supports open access (OA) journals). Nevertheless, in this case also, the strategic value of such an index potentially implies that no further effort will be spent to ensure a journal's visibility in other indexes. Another similar dimension of this primary screening process is related to the scope of an index: whether it is specific to a discipline area, or many disciplines areas, or it is simply a catch-all index. Such a criteria allows to pick appropriate indexes for a given journal, but also contributes to limiting an exhaustive perception of the indexing landscape.

Indeed, while the aforementioned strategy and scope criteria bring an efficient and clear selection process, they do not fully address the complexity of the landscape, which is due to the very different types of the indexes. First of all, indexes can be either open or closed, with a difference in terms of visibility impact that is hard to measure: being visible on an index whose validation is demanding ensures that some quality standards will be reached, but with potentially little visibility to the targeted research community. For instance, the criteria to enter some proprietary indexes are built upon publishing practices proper to a limited

⁴ List of academic databases and search engines. (2024, July 2). In *Wikipedia*.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_academic_databases_and_search_engines

number of disciplines and statistically limit the amount of other disciplines' publications represented in the index. In such a case, researchers of the less represented disciplines may look for resources in other indexes, and the quality validation obtained by the journal that joined the proprietary index has therefore a limited effect on its actual visibility.

Another important difference between indexes is related to their data collection process, i.e., the method used to record bibliographic information and useful links about the journals and their articles. Some indexes collect the information they display through manual processes and updates, others through automated processes, like the metadata harvesting via the OAI-PMH (Open Archive Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) protocol. Indeed, requirements for automated processes essentially imply a high standardization level of the information made available in order to make it manageable in the digital environment. Such processes require therefore a certain level of digital skills and an appropriate assessment of the workflow complexity. At the same time, like already mentioned, contrary to what happens in most cases with closed indexes, the automated processes essentially rely on interoperability purposes, which ensure a higher level of discoverability: the effort required to achieve extended interoperability can be therefore more rewarding in terms of discoverability than reaching the specific standards of a platform that may be less connected with the whole digital ecosystem.

The interoperability dimension introduces another major difference between the various indexes: the series of additional services and features proposed in combination with their main service related to indexing. For instance, interoperability features do not only allow for an increased dissemination, but also to potential further reuse within knowledge graphs establishing connections between the index records. The indexes can also include metrics services, about usage and citations of the publications referenced. Some indexes include the display of the full text by default, or even operate as a publishing platform. It is almost impossible to list here all the additional services proposed by the indexes, but such services precisely add another complexity level in the assessment and selection process of the appropriate index for a given journal.

This quick overview gives a first notion of the difficulty for the publishers to identify the right index for their journal and to assess the specific effort required to be referenced on each index. Indeed, the difference in terms of validation process between indexes implies differences in time and human resource investment. The difference in terms of data collection process implies a different set of skills, or the necessity to rely on institutional or external technical support. It seems therefore crucial in this context to provide a global set of information to the publishers. Furthermore, as the landscape of academic publications' indexing is constantly evolving, thus adding another degree of complexity, the information provided has to be regularly updated, and structured information will make this updating process easier.

2.3 Representing and Understanding the Landscape

Diamond publishers may have difficulties to seize the full complexity of the indexing landscape either because of a lack of knowledge, or skills, or time, or simply interest, but even

more expert actors, better acquainted with such services, can experience the same difficulty given the wide variety described above. The difficulty starts actually from the very beginning: how to name them? Is there, not a single term, but at least a series of terms, well enough defined and shared, to indicate the types of academic publications' indexing services? The short answer is "no", even if we opted in the context of this task for a broadly acceptable solution, which still requires some explanation.

It has first to be noted that those services do not describe themselves in a consistent manner. Search engine, index, directory, catalog, database, aggregator are not perfectly interchangeable terms, nevertheless, they describe services that, on one hand, have common aspects related to their action of referencing scholarly publications which do not always seem to justify a different naming. On the other hand, they have differences that their names do not make clearly explicit. In some cases, services relying on the same processes have different names: while they both essentially collect and display bibliographic references, Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE) defines itself as a "search engine" and OpenAlex as a "catalog", for no clear reason. The two services do have some remarkable differences, however, these do not appear to be well expressed by their self-definitions.

These typology terms correspond actually sometimes to a specific perspective: "search engine" represents the service perspective, and indicates what the service effectuates; "database" represents the technological perspective, and indicates how the service is built; "directory" represents the content perspective, and indicates the nature of what will be found on the service; "aggregator" represents the operational perspective, and indicates how the service operates, etc. The typology terms can also correspond to a specific usage. "Catalog", for instance, comes from the library sector, and refers to the catalog of the collections in a given institution, although with the digital turn, the boundaries of such catalogs are harder to define. "Database" comes from the information science sector, and refers to the information system underlying the service, rather than being the service itself. In fact, all these terms can describe the same object from different perspectives: a directory holds a database that can be populated through data aggregation and offered to the public as a search engine. Furthermore, the marketing aspect of this naming ("catalog" connotes an exhaustive collection reminding the reliability of library catalogs, "database" connotes technical soundness and rigor, etc.) confuses further the linguistic clarity and justifies to not enter in pointless definition debates. For all these reasons, it has been decided in T5.1 to opt for a practical solution and use "index" as the broader term, even if it is not completely neutral. While in the library sector, but also in the publishing sector, "index" rather refers to the indexing of a content's topics, or named entities, according to a controlled list of terms, it is also used in information technology and database management to indicate the ordering of the database entries. Nevertheless, intended as an organized list of items that may only be referenced, but not held, "index" seems to be the most generic term able to include all the specific types listed above.

The fact remains, however, that those indexes fulfill their core mission in distinct ways, especially from the perspective, which again is our main concern here, of their data provider. If the typology terms alone do not seem to appropriately describe the services, at least in an easy and commonly accepted way, a categorization effort still seems to be useful. Even more so, as the T5.1 collects information about a wide variety of indexes, some consistent

organization of the information is required. Usually, detailed documentation on indexes focuses on specific services and a community's specific needs. In these cases, documentation is offered only for major indexing services. For instance, in France, the Centre Mersenne⁵ provides support to scholarly communication, with a slight priority given to Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) disciplines: it provides documentation on how to be referenced on WoS, Scopus, PubMed, Mathematical reviews, and the French national open archive HAL. Although this documentation served as an inspiration for T5.1 output, it does not offer the global view that is necessary for the task to organize its heterogeneous material.

Attempts to describe in a structured way the indexing services landscape as such are indeed not that many, leaving the OADJs without appropriate orientation tools. We already mentioned the Wikipedia list, and we can see in this example that the authors of the encyclopedia article opted for a simple solution, making the distinction only between "Full-text aggregators" and "Metadata services"⁶. The first category contains examples such as PubMed Central (PMC), Connecting Repositories (CORE), Semantic Scholar; the second one, examples such as BASE, DOAJ, Google Scholar – and CORE again. The two lists also indicate the disciplinary perimeter, the access cost, and the provider of the service. These categories and their specifications, although rather broad, give a useful structure from a user perspective: they indicate what one could find and to which conditions on each of these services. Nevertheless, with the possibility of hyperlinking, it is not sure that the "Full text" category is really relevant and that it is as useful as specifying if this full text is OA or not. More generally, it does not describe the specificities of the services (there is little in common between BASE, DOAJ, and Google Scholar) and therefore brings little help to data providers like OADJs.

A more sophisticated classification was proposed by the French University of Bordeaux in a guide about referencing, targeting this time the academic publishers⁷. The guide distinguishes the following categories:

- Catalogs handled by libraries and documentation centers: a global example is Worldcat, other examples include national and university libraries;
- Indexes based on the access type: DOAJ⁸ and Directory of Open Access scholarly Resources (ROAD)⁹;

⁵ <https://www.centre-mersenne.org/en/>

⁶ Interestingly, the encyclopaedia article starts by making a distinction between "databases" and "search engines", but concretely uses, for more clarity, this full text / metadata distinction when establishing its lists. Moreover, "metadata services" often operate through aggregation, so this new distinction also has limitations. See "List of academic databases and search engines" (2024).

⁷ Benharrat, A., Louison, S. (2022) *Guide pour le référencement des revues scientifiques en Arts, Lettres, Langues, Sciences Humaines et Sociales (ALLSHS)*. Université Bordeaux Montaigne; Direction de la recherche. https://www.doi.org/10.46608/guideref_allshs

⁸ <https://doaj.org/>

⁹ <https://road.issn.org/>

- Bibliometric databases: Scopus¹⁰, WoS¹¹;
- Search engines: Google Scholar¹², BASE¹³, Dimensions¹⁴, Semantic Scholar¹⁵, ISIDORE¹⁶;
- Index fed by the journals: ERIH PLUS¹⁷, MIAR¹⁸;
- Open Archives: HAL¹⁹.

Although more interesting and useful for our case, the classification, as we can see, actually combines different types of criteria. The category based on the access type is related to the scope and does not tell how the service operates. The category “bibliometric databases” is useful to identify the specificity of two of the main referencing indexes, but the term “database” does not correspond to their complex admission process. Like in the Wikipedia list, we find again the “search engine” type, which is indeed a very distinct type, especially from the point of view of the data provider, as they operate through automated processes. Overall, this guide provides a rather limited number and clear set of categories. Leaving aside longer discussions about the categories’ definition or name, it is possible to infer and reuse from this classification some analytical criteria able to describe a wide range of indexing services.

The French Mir@bel²⁰ service made an additional effort, partially aligned with this classification, to represent the complex indexing services landscape through a mind map²¹. Some categories are essentially identical: academic institutional catalogs and the bibliometric services, the latter also here represented by Scopus and WoS. Some categories are renamed: “search engines” become “semantic search engines”, which at least in the case of Google Scholar seems inaccurate; “open archives” become “full text aggregators”, although the HAL example might be better described as a “full text repository”. In other cases, the service is defined in a different way: DOAJ is not defined here through its scope, but through its admission process as a “qualitative” service. Similarly, and reversely, ERIH PLUS is not defined anymore through its admission process, but through its scope, the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). These last two examples confirm that it is difficult to describe indexing services from one angle only. Finally, the mind map also adds a new category with the

¹⁰ <https://www.scopus.com/home.uri>

¹¹ <https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-discovery-and-workflow-solutions/webofscience-platform/>

¹² <https://scholar.google.com/>

¹³ <https://www.base-search.net/>

¹⁴ <https://www.dimensions.ai/>

¹⁵ <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>

¹⁶ <https://isidore.science/>

¹⁷ <https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringsskanaler/erihplus/>. Although this category is not very clearly defined by the authors of the ERIH PLUS team, it seems inaccurate in the case of ERIH PLUS, which does not accept submissions from the publishers themselves.

¹⁸ <https://miar.ub.edu/>

¹⁹ <https://hal.science/>

²⁰ <https://reseau-mirabel.info/>

²¹ Tessier, B. (2022, November 8). Systèmes de référencement de publications scientifiques. Mindomo. <https://www.mindomo.com/fr/mindmap/systemes-de-referencement-des-publications-scientifiques-8-nov-2022-e1c1376c0b904de48c78677b4a6b50fc> (in French only).

“bibliographic” type, represented for instance by the EBSCO services, which are indeed operating in a specific way in the referencing landscape, providing strictly intended bibliographic references.

While all these examples may seem to discourage from any attempt to produce a satisfactory and exhaustive classification, they actually provide, as we already mentioned, a useful set of analytical criteria, a series of crucial and distinct elements of information which may not lead to a clear list of terms and definitions, but at least to a structured way of presenting this information. This is indeed on this basis that the T5.1 built its KB, as a first step to establish the indexing services documentation.

2.4 Indexes Knowledge Base (KB)

2.4.1 Summary

Before starting to draft the documentation, which is the main output of the T5.1, it has been decided to collect and store information in a structured KB²². The objective was to record information about the indexes in a consistent manner that would allow for exhaustivity and comparison, ensuring that all services will be described according to the same criteria. The KB is not however meant to be a substitute to the extensive documentation of complex admission processes: it rather gives a complete overview of the service allowing OADJs to assess its specific requirements, challenges, and benefits, and eventually explore further their admission process. As stated before, the KB structure tries to take into account the existing examples of indexing services lists, using and extending their analytical criteria. The KB was designed as a source for the documentation and contains more extensive details about, for instance, technical aspects or features. With this in mind, the KB will also be made available to the public, as a separate output, but complementary to the documentation.

2.4.2 Building the KB

The KB contains three main sections, plus a few additional fields.

- The first section contains general information about the service: a first series of information about the service administration and identity, and another series about the service's operation and provision.
- The second section focuses on information more directly useful to the OADJs, describing the joining process, the types of contents accepted, the requirements for journals and articles, especially the editorial requirements and the ones related to metadata.
- The third section gives details about the data management process, in particular the protocol or method used to collect data and handle it in the service's information system.

²² See Annex 7.1.

- The additional fields give information about the complementary services offered besides the indexing. They also provide free text information about the bibliodiversity support of the services, as this support might be of particular interest for the OADJs.

The KB structure was established progressively through iteration and testing. A first version was established and tested against the examples of BASE and Google Scholar, as the two services operate in very different ways. The BASE example, together with the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) example, led to describe more in detail the metadata requirements, as these services have different levels of importance for the metadata (mandatory, recommended, optional). The Google Scholar example led to adding a specific field for the Search Engine Optimization (SEO) requirements. Other services helped to refine further the KB structure in order to make sure, on one hand, that no crucial information would be missed, but also, on the other, that the additional information corresponded to a characteristic common to at least two services. The current version is the third one, but the development of the documentation may imply other updates.

The KB was therefore simultaneously and progressively structured and populated. A first empirical list of indexing services was established, based on their importance for academic journals in general or OADJs in particular. The first list consisted of: BASE, Central and Eastern European Online Library (CEEOL), Dimension, DOAJ²³, EBSCO, ERIH PLUS, Google Scholar²⁴, GoTriple, Latindex, OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, PubMed, ROAD, Scopus, Semantic Scholar, and WoS. The list gathered services different in types, geographical coverage, scope, access types, and was representative of the global landscape. Internal discussions led later to adding national indexing services as well, as it could be valuable for OADJs to find structured information on regional services. The work of populating the KB was at this stage distributed among the task's partners, including partners representing some of the services (i.e., DOAJ, OpenAIRE and HRČAK), in order to obtain a first representative amount of KB entries fully described. It was then possible, based on the new entries and some interpretations issues between the partners, to refine further the KB structure and arrive at the version 3, which is the one currently used.

2.4.3 Next Steps

Regarding the KB structure, the next steps included an alignment with the documentation, as in the writing process some fields naming and content appeared to need some clarification. Additional adjustments may also be needed to correctly address specificities of new entries. Another related important next action will be the alignment within the KB of the already described entries, in order to make sure that each field of the KB contains the same type of information type for all the KB entries. For what concerns the current list of indexes, the immediate next step, after the alignments mentioned before will be achieved, will be to

²³ See Annex 7.2.

²⁴ See Annex 7.3.

continue populating the KB with the entries that have not yet been described. However, the remaining entries to describe are not many, and the main focus, and challenge, will be to decide which and how many other entries to add into the KB, taking into account the extended list provided in the Wikipedia page.

2.5 Indexes Typology

From an internal task's workshop around the index's typology emerged the idea to provide a single table with all the indexes and actionable filters to compare and select them. Indeed, instead of a limited list of broad types, or an extensive list with few filters, it has been deemed more useful for OADJs and academic publishers in general to have all the indexes described according to a limited but precise set of criteria. The list is currently a simple spreadsheet, with criteria used in filtering columns, but a more user-friendly format may be designed later. Although not planned as such in the Description of Action (DoA), the indexes typology table could be an additional output of the task, alongside with the KB and the documentation files. The index typology is at this stage a work in progress. The current list of criteria considered are the following:

Category	Criteria			
Index content	full text (digital object)	link to the full text included in metadata by default	bibliographic metadata	
Data collection	automated data collection (harvesting)	manual entry (by content provider)	Extraction of metadata from PDF	
Evaluation	Metadata quality	Editorial quality		
Metrics	Citations	Usage (visits, downloads, altmetric data etc.)		

Scope	Multidisciplinary (all disciplines)	Disciplinary	Geographic (country, region)	Institutional (one or more institutions)	Type of access
Search features	Simple Search	Advanced Search	Filters	Semantic enrichments	
Data dissemination and reuse	Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API)	OAI-PMH	Metadata dump		

Table 1: Indexes typology criteria

2.6 Classification and Its Usage

From the previous reflections made and methods applied, it appears that some main characteristics of the indexes emerge, although an exhaustive classification universally applicable may still not be possible. There are two main reasons for this impossibility. First, the indexes can have characteristics that belong to more than one category. Second, the classification itself may not correspond to the practices and understanding of each and every user. Precisely, however, the classification effort has a particular importance in terms of usage for our specific project. While the description of each service through the documentation and the filtering features proposed through the Typology table both facilitate the understanding of individual services, a classification, even approximative, with broader categories would bring a useful clarification of the landscape. Furthermore, some important distinctions can also have an impact in the building of the DDH. Indeed, as the DDH will collect and expose data, the data collection process of the indexes has obviously an impact on how OADJs data will be able to appear on the DDH.

From this point of view, the data collection process can result in a classification useful both for OADJs and the DDH. It is indeed possible to make a distinction between those types of data collection:

- Web crawling (GScholar, OpenAlex)
- Harvesting data exposed via OAI repositories (OpenAIRE, BASE, GoTriple)
- Data pushed to indexes via API (DOAJ, Crossref, PubMed) or manual submission (via Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP) or webform).

Another important distinction, both for the OADJs and the DDH, is the evaluation perimeter, as it is reported already in the Typology table. The fact that the evaluation considers only technical aspects, or also editorial ones, corresponds to a major classification dichotomy, that has, besides the interest of a clarification of the landscape, a direct impact on the classification usage: OADJs and the DDH may discard one of these types for feasibility or policy reasons.

Such a preliminary analysis will be further detailed in the second version of the report, once the KB and the related index documentation will be enriched and stabilized. In this further stage, broad classifications like the ones mentioned above will help OADJs to select the appropriate index for their title. In relation to this work, it is also planned to provide the KB in a more reusable and actionable format, which will facilitate its publication, on one hand, but also, on the other, potentially allow for automated processing and comparison.

APPROVAL PENDING

3 OUTPUT: INDEX DOCUMENTATION

3.1 From the KB to the Documentation

The creation of the index documentation is supported by the KB. Its aim is to give, especially to OADJs, an overview of the main indexes and aggregators used in the academic field. With respect to the KB, the documentation is a less detailed and more accessible description of the index designed to give synthetic information. In order to create this documentation, we essentially chose information types that were already in the KB. A few information types were either specified (e.g. “publishing history”) or added (e.g. “number of items” in the index); these adaptations allowed for a further refinement of the KB. With a length of around three to four pages, this documentation is intended to be easily readable and can be supplemented if necessary by an in-depth reading of the KB.

This documentation is divided into three main sections:

- General Information
- Content and Service
- Requirements for Academic Publications

Each section is subdivided into detailed fields (see the full template in Annex 7.4).

The first one “General Information” allows the publishers to have a concise view of the global aspects of the index. The second section describes the indexes’ “Content and Service”. This section aims at explaining which and how journal's information is displayed in order to help OADJs determine whether their title belongs in this index. The third and final section is the “Requirements for Academic Publications”. It describes the requirements and criteria of the index. The objective here is to give a precise description of the admission criteria that are either mandatory or recommended to join the index. More specifically, this section helps publishers to estimate the journal’s chances to join the index and eventually the journal’s modifications needed to increase the compliance with the requirements.

- General Information

This first section “General Information” is about the administrative and general aspects of the index. It displays an overall view about the index’s status, its owner and launch year, but also the scope covered by the index. This section also mentions the type of access for the users and for the data providers. We also indicate links to the index documentation and application form, when it exists, to help the publishers navigate the information displayed by the index website.

- Content and Service

The second section is about the index “Content and Service”. The aim of this section is to describe the type and the management of the items referenced on the index. For example, the content language and the index sources. This way, OADJs can gather elements of information about the environment where their contents will appear, in order to help them choose the most suitable. This part also displays more technical information. The first one is about the index sources. For some indexes the main sources are journals registered in the platform, but other indexes aggregate data from other databases to maximize the number of indexed resources. Another part of the documentation displays information about the supported standards. These standards present the metadata model applied by the index to the metadata they collect and manage; the list contains all the standards supported by the index, and it can be slightly more extended than the standards actually required from the data providers. This information is valuable for the OADJs to know exactly which metadata model they have to apply to their contents. We end the “Content and Services” section with a presentation of the index bibliodiversity support, giving more specific details on languages supported by the platform but also about the openness of the resources accessible.

- Requirements for Academic Publications

The third section is about the requirements of the index. Here are provided details about the steps and verifications an OADJ needs to make before submission to the index. This part is divided into three subsections. The first one is about the “Joining Process”. It describes the procedures that publishers have to follow to submit their journal. For some indexes that automatically collect data, no specific actions are required for the journal’s submission. In other cases indexes can ask for a registration and general information about the journal to validate the submission. The data collection process is also an important information type that appears in the documentation. It describes technologies and processes used by the index to collect the journal’s metadata. Having a better understanding of this process allows publishers to prepare their metadata for their integration in the index. It can also appear as a requirement when the data collection made by the index needs specific standards of metadata to be applied. It’s the case for example with the GoTriple index.

The next subsection focuses on the criteria the journal needs to meet to be part of the index. We subdivided each subsection to be more precise and clearer about this type of information. When no such requirements exist, subsection is removed. The “Minimum Requirements”, as the expression tells, inform OADJs about the basic criteria that will allow them to be referenced. This part is divided into two parts: “Editorial Requirements” and “Technical Requirements”. The “Editorial Requirements” are more detailed than the one in the KB to better address the needs of the publishers and is subdivided into four subsections. This category can contain information about the journal history required by the index but also the

composition of the editorial board or the subject area the journal must cover to be part of the index.

For the “Technical Requirements” field, we reuse information types already in the KB because of their accuracy. The “Technical Requirements” section is subdivided into four subsections. The first two subsections “Metadata Standard” and “Data File Format” focus on the formatting effort required, either regarding the data format or the metadata standard. In the metadata standard subsection are only listed the standards required by the index, while in the previous “Content and service” section, the “Supported Standards” describe all the standards handled or used by the index. Some indexes ask indeed for specific standards to be applied, for example OpenAIRE requires the metadata to use at a minimum the Dublin Core standard, together with the Datacite or OpenAIRE standards for some specific metadata fields. In such cases, publishers have the responsibility to produce themselves the standardized metadata. Finally, we also give the list of all metadata mandatory fields. These fields can be very diverse in terms of number and precision from one index to another.

The “Additional Criteria and/or Specifications” subsection lists either recommended specifications that publishers can leave aside, or specifications that the indexes may optionally check. This subsection aims to give the publishers a list of elements that can improve the journal’s evaluation by the index, or its global interoperability, but that are not necessary for being included in the index. The structure used here is very similar to the one used for “Minimum Requirements”, as it uses a division between editorial and technical specifications. They can cover quality evaluations that will be made by the index. For example the evaluation of the journal’s target audience. They can also specify, besides the minimum required metadata standard, additional metadata standards that can be handled by the index. Finally, we also add an optional metadata subcategory that can be specified to allow for a better description of the journal. For example, the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of the resource, the keywords or an abstract of the resource.

The flexibility of this documentation’s structure can be observed when applied to two very different indexes such as DOAJ and OpenAIRE. If the documentation about “General Information” and “Content and Service” can be easily completed for the two indexes their respective requirements are very different and necessitate the use of a large set of subsections. In the case of DOAJ there are several minimum and optional editorial criteria. For example, a publishing history of more than one year, the name and affiliation of all editors and board members must be included, the fact that no embargo can be applied by the journal, and so on. But there are fewer technical requirements than the ones specified by OpenAIRE. Indeed, OpenAIRE has no editorial requirements, but has much more requirements dedicated to the standardization of the information. For example, both the metadata required and recommended metadata are very precise and cover diverse standards.

This documentation has been designed to adapt to the diversity of indexes. It also gives an easy-to-use orientation tool in a multiplicity of index information and requirements. With this representation of the index, publishers can compare indexes and choose the most suitable for their journal. If the two first sections about the indexes' general information and the content and service easily apply to all indexes, the other sections vary greatly as already mentioned in case of editorial and technical requirements, as well as the joining process. This documentation aims to organize and structure index information with sections left empty if no information is indicated. This level of information granularity allows to easily edit and update the documentation. All pieces of information are separate from each other in a way that makes possible their modification without compromising the integrity of the entire document. With this organization we hope that the structure of the documentation will be easily editable and can be adapted to a large diversity of index profiles.

3.2 Documentation on Major Indexes

3.2.1 Directory of Open Access Journals

Community-curated list of peer-reviewed OA journals, maintained by Infrastructure Services for Open Access (IS4OA). DOAJ also allows for article metadata collection and display, and free distribution of journal and article metadata.

General information

Name	Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Website	https://doaj.org/
Owner	Infrastructure Services for Open Access
Owner type	Non-profit organization
Owner country	UK / Denmark
Launch year	2003
Scope	Any
Number of items	Above 20 000 journals, Above 10 million articles
Access for index users	free
Access for index data providers	free
Documentation	

Criteria documentation: https://doaj.org/apply/guide/
Application form for providers
https://doaj.org/account/login?redirected=apply

Content and service

Content type	Journals, Articles
Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	134 countries represented
Indexing level for publications	Journal
Full text	link to the full text available
Index sources	Journal
Supported standards	Dublin Core, DOAJ and Crossref schemas
Additional services	
<p>Journals are Preserved Forever (JASPER) (project for open access journals preservation): https://doaj.org/preservation/</p> <p>Transparency and best practice (guidelines): https://doaj.org/apply/transparency/</p> <p>Think. Check. Submit. (Trusted publisher identification for research): https://thinkchecksubmit.org/</p> <p>Publishers Learning and Community Exchange (PLACE): https://theplace.discourse.group/</p> <p>OA Journals Toolkit: https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/fr</p>	
Bibliodiversity support	
World-wide coverage of countries and languages in OA (Gold and Diamond OA)	

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Publishers have to register and complete an online application form: <https://doaj.org/account/login?redirected=apply>

The admission requires compliance with a set of editorial and technical requirements.

Data Collection

Journal information is recorded during the submission process, through an online web form in the first place.

Once this submission is validated article information can be then uploaded and updated in various ways:

- manually on DOAJ's website using a dedicated web form to enter metadata;
- through the DOAJ API using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) files;
- through Extensible Markup Language (XML) upload following DOAJ²⁵ or Crossref schemas²⁶.

Extensive details about these processes are available here: <https://doaj.org/docs/faq/>

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

Journal and Publishing History

- Journal publishes at least five research articles per year
- Publishing history of more than one year or have published at least ten OA research articles

Editorial Board

- Journal must have an editor and an editorial board listed on the website
- Name and affiliation of all editors and board must be included
- Information on the editorial board must be accessible

²⁵ DOAJ Native XML (XSD: <https://www.doaj.org/static/doaj/doajArticles.xsd>).

²⁶ Crossref 4.4.2 XML (XSD: <https://www.doaj.org/static/crossref/crossref4.4.2.xsd>); Crossref 5.3.1 XML (XSD: <https://www.doaj.org/static/crossref/crossref5.3.1.xsd>).

Publishing Policy

- Peer review process (with two independent reviewers and details on the process available on the website)
- Any research subject area
- No embargo
- Aims and scope informations must be accessible
- Instruction for authors must be accessible
- Informations on author charges and fees must be accessible
- Informations about contact details must be accessible (journal email address, contact person)

Copyright

Journals where the copyright holder of a scholarly work grants usage rights to others using an open license (Creative Commons or equivalent). This allows for immediate free access to the work and permits any user to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose.

Technical Minimum Requirements

Data File Format

- Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) or PDF

Metadata File Format

- XML, JSON, Webform (text)

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- Journal title
- International Standard Serial Number (ISSN)
- Electronic International Standard Serial Number (e-ISSN)

Additional Criteria/Specifications

Editorial Additional Specifications

Editorial Board

- Editorial board for the journal should consist of at least five editors with appropriate qualifications and expertise (recommended that board members not all come from the same institution)
- Name and affiliations of reviewers if displayed

Publishing Policy

- Endogeneity should be minimized (portion of published research papers where at least one of the authors is an editor or editorial board member)
- Use of plagiarism checking service is highly recommended

3.2.2 ERIH PLUS

ERIH PLUS is an online index holding bibliographic information on academic journals in the SSH, with a focus on quality journals across all European languages and countries. ERIH PLUS supports journals' policies of openness and transparency in line with editorial best practices. Curation ensures that journals OA status and Plan S compliance is marked. ERIH PLUS offers an additional index of articles, which is an SSH subset of Dimensions collections, showing only articles having a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Dimensions is a multidisciplinary database that brings together over 140 million publications.

General Information

Name	ERIH PLUS
Website	https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/
Owner	Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research
Owner type	Public research organization
Owner country	Norway
Launch year	2014
Scope	Social Science and Humanities
Number of items	Above 10 million articles
Access for index users	Free
Access for index data providers	Free upon registration and not affiliated with the journals (publishers and members of the editorial board)
Documentation	
Criteria documentation: https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/about/criteria_for_inclusion	

Application form for providers

<https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringsskanaler/erihplus/login.action>

Content and Service

Content type	Journals, articles (with Dimensions)
Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	Journals. The articles indexing is fully automated (powered by Dimensions) and does not require any additional action. The article metadata displayed thus depends strictly on the Crossref information collected by Dimensions.
Full text	Link to the full text when available
Index sources	Journals and Dimensions / Crossref
Supported standards	Internal metadata format
Additional services	Records show if the journal is indexed in other indexes (e. g. DOAJ, Securing a Hybrid Environment for Research Preservation and Access (SHERPA)/Rights Metadata for Open Archiving (RoMEO). ERIH PLUS Record connects with Plan S Journal Checker tool: https://journalcheckertool.org/ External support from Dimensions to display metadata about articles: https://www.dimensions.ai/
Bibliodiversity support	
No limitations on the content language	

ERIH PLUS focuses on SSH disciplines usually less represented in private indexes at the core of the impact factor evaluation. Journals in these areas published outside Europe can also be accepted if "used by European scholars".

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

New journals have to be submitted after creation of a user account:

<https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringsskanaler/erihplus/login.action>

ERIH PLUS will not be evaluating journals submitted by publishers, members of the editorial board or others affiliated with a journal.

Data Collection

- Journal metadata are collected upon manual submission
- Articles metadata indexing is automated and powered by Dimensions

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

Journal and Publishing History

- Two years of publication

Editorial Board

- List of the members of the academic editorial board, and their affiliations

Publishing Policy

- English abstract available online
- SSH subject area
- Peer review and explicit description of the journal's procedure for independent peer review. (not affiliated with the authors...)
- Informations about authors affiliations for all scholarly articles for the last two years of publication (fill university names, email or postal address)
- No more than two thirds of the authors published in the journal are from the same institution (reviewing the last two years of publication)

Technical Minimum Requirements

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- ISSN (confirmed by the international ISSN Portal)
- publication language
- publisher's country
- publishing house (if applicable)
- publisher

Additional Criteria/Specifications

Editorial Optional Specifications

Journal History

- Publication history of at least two years

Publishing Policy

- Evaluation of the target audience of the journal
- Statement on ethical publishing
- Relevant journal for European researchers / research area
- Presence of the journal in other indexes

Copyright

- OA status
- Evaluation of the Article Processing Charges (APC) policy

3.2.3 GoTriple

GoTriple is a multilingual discovery platform for the SSH. It provides a comprehensive access point for discovering and reusing research artifacts that are relevant to the wide variety of disciplines under the umbrella domain of SSH: publications and research data, project descriptions, authors and researcher profiles are automatically imported from aggregators and source providers, semantically enriched and linked in GoTriple.

General Information

Name	GoTriple
Website	https://www.gotriple.eu/
Owner	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS RI)
Owner type	Non-profit organization
Owner country	Belgium
Launch year	2021
Scope	Social Sciences and Humanities
Number of items	15 million documents
Access for index users	Free
Access for index data providers	Free
Documentation	
About metadata requirements: https://www.gotriple.eu/docs/gotriple-handbook-v1_0.pdf	
About data submission: https://www.gotriple.eu/docs/your_data_in_gotriple-v1_0.pdf	
Application form for providers	
https://pipeline.gotriple.eu/user/login?destination=/	

Content and Service

Content type	Publications, Datasets, Projects, Profiles
Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	Article
Full text	Link to the full text if available
Index sources	DOAJ Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) ISIDORE OpenAIRE BASE Europeana Biblioteka Nauki
Supported standards	Dublin Core OpenAIRE format Europeana Data Model (EDM) Machine-Readable Cataloging21 (MARC21) (work in progress) Schema.org (internal use only)
Additional services	
<p>Search visualization: https://openknowledgemaps.org/</p> <p>Online annotation tool: https://thepund.it/</p> <p>GoTriple APIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endpoint: https://api.gotriple.eu/ • Documentation: https://zenodo.org/records/7371832 	
Bibliodiversity support	
<p>GoTriple collects mostly metadata about OA resources, however the index contains records of some closed access contents.</p> <p>Multilingualism support:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic classification of the content in 27 SSH disciplines in 11 languages. 	

- Automatic annotation of the content with the [TRIPLE Vocabulary](#) which provides a hierarchical set of over 3.300 SSH-related concepts in 12 languages.
- The user interface is localized in 9 languages.

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

If the publications are not already stored in GoTriple's data sources, the main option is to register a new data source through the dedicated interface:

<https://pipeline.gotriple.eu/user/login?destination=/>.

Data Collection

In order to be referenced on GoTriple it is necessary to provide a standard access to standard metadata, i.e. providing an [OAI-PMH](#) repository with metadata in the standards supported by GoTriple.

It is also possible to send a file formatted according to the [OpenAIRE format](#).

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

The publication has to be a scholarly output in the SSH area. It can correspond to a variety of types: article, bibliography, blog-post, report, periodical, preprint, review, etc.

Technical Minimum Requirements

Metadata Standard

- Dublin Core

Metadata File Format

- XML
- JSON

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- Creator of the resource
- Identifier of the resource
- Title of the resource

Additional Criteria/Specifications

Technical Additional Specifications

Metadata Standard

- OpenAIRE format
- EDM
- MARC21 (work in progress)

Metadata Recommended Fields

- Abstract
- Access rights to the resource
- Date of publication or creation
- Keywords
- Language of the resource
- License
- Publisher of the resource
- Type of the resource
- URL of the landing page
- URL of the resource
- URL of the source

Metadata Optional Fields

- Contributor to the resource's creation
- Format of the resource
- Information on the source
- Temporal coverage of the resource
- Spatial coverage of the resource

3.2.4 Google Scholar

Searchable bibliographic index that displays full text and metadata of scholarly literature across an array of publishing formats and disciplines.

General information

Name	Google Scholar
Website	https://scholar.google.com/
Owner	Google
Owner type	Private company
Owner country	USA
Launch year	2004
Scope	Any
Number of items	Approximately 389 million scholarly documents ²⁷
Access for index users	Free
Access for index data providers	Free
Documentation	
Technical inclusion guidelines: https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/inclusion.html	
Indexation guidelines: https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/inclusion.html#indexing	
Application form for providers	
None	

²⁷ Gusenbauer, M. (2019). Google Scholar to overshadow them all? Comparing the sizes of 12 academic search engines and bibliographic databases. *Scientometrics*, 118, 177-214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-018-2958-5>

Content and Service

Content type	Scholarly articles (Journal papers, conference papers, technical reports, or their drafts, dissertations, pre-prints, post-prints, or abstracts)
Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	Articles
Full text	link to the full text when available
Index sources	Any website with scholarly articles and proper URL
Supported standards	HTML meta tags supporting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highwire Press tags - BE Press tags - PRISM tags - Dublin Core tags
Additional services	<p>Google scholar Metrics (visibility and influence of recent articles in scholarly publications): https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/metrics.html</p> <p>Google scholar Profiles (showcase of authors publications): https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/citations.html</p>
Bibliodiversity support	
No limitation on the language of the content or the publishing business model	

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Google Scholar uses automated software, known as “robots” or “crawlers”, to fetch files for inclusion in the search results. The journal’s website needs to be structured in a way that makes it possible to “crawl” in this manner. Automatic crawlers need to be able to discover

and fetch the URLs of all articles, as well as to periodically refresh their content from the journal website.

Data Collection

- Web crawling

Minimum Requirements

Technical Minimum Requirements

Data File Format

- HTML or PDF

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- For PDF publications:
 - Title (large font)
 - Authors (below title)
 - Bibliographic citation of the paper (in first page footer)
- Bibliography (separate section) For HTML publications (metadata included in metatags of the HTML file):
 - Title
 - Authors
 - Publication date
 - Bibliographic citation of the paper
 - Bibliography

3.2.5 OpenAIRE Graph

The OpenAIRE Graph is an open resource that aggregates a collection of research data properties (metadata, links) available within the OpenAIRE Open Science infrastructure for funders, organizations, researchers, research communities and publishers. It is made available via datasets published on Zenodo and searchable via OpenAIRE EXPLORE.

General Information

Name	OpenAIRE Graph
Website	https://graph.openaire.eu/
Owner	OpenAIRE AMKE
Owner type	Non-profit Partnership (NPP)
Owner country	European Union (EU) (legal location Greece)
Launch year	2010
Scope	Any
Number of items	176 million publications
Access for index users	Free
Access for index data providers	Free
Documentation	
	Guidelines for repository managers: https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0/
Application form for providers	
	https://provide.openaire.eu/home

Content and Service

Content type	Articles, datasets, software
Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	Any

Indexing level for publications	Articles
Full text	Link to the full text if the publication is in OA and the data source gives their consent
Index sources	<p>Institutional/Thematic repositories</p> <p>Aggregators</p> <p>Journal/publisher archives</p> <p>Institutional/National Current Research Information Systems (CRIS)</p> <p>Metadata catalogues</p> <p>Scholarly communication sources (e.g. Crossref, Datacite, Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID), DOAJ)</p> <p>Full list of data sources here: https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find/dataproviders</p>
Supported standards	Datacite, Dublin Core
Additional services	<p>OpenAIRE EXPLORE (A comprehensive and open dataset of research information) https://explore.openaire.eu/</p> <p>OpenAIRE CONNECT (An overlay platform to share, link, disseminate and monitor publications) https://connect.openaire.eu/</p> <p>OpenAIRE MONITOR (A tool to discover, track and understand trends and impact pathways for organizations) https://monitor.openaire.eu/</p> <p>OpenAIRE PROVIDE (Service for content providers to interact with OpenAIRE) https://provide.openaire.eu/home</p> <p>OpenAIRE Broker (Service for content providers to complete and enrich metadata of their registered scholarly works) https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker/overview</p> <p>OpenAIRE UsageCounts (Service that collects and aggregates usage data from Open Science content providers repositories, journals, and other scientific data sources.)</p>

<https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/>

Zenodo (universal repository of all research outcomes)

<https://zenodo.org/>

Bibliodiversity support

Metadata is available in many different languages like Japanese, Russian and Indonesian. The website is only in english. The search works also on non-english metadata, with some difficulties on logographic or complex alphabets like chinese and japanese

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

If the publications are not already stored in OpenAIRE's data source (full list of data sources here: <https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find/dataproviders>), the main option is to register the data source via OpenAIRE PROVIDE (<https://provide.openaire.eu/>). The data source must be compliant with the OpenAIRE guidelines (<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/>).

Data Collection

- Upon submission by OpenAIRE PROVIDE
- Automatic collection of metadata via OAI-PMH and REST APIs. The metadata provided need to follow OpenAIRE guidelines: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

Minimum Requirements

Technical Minimum Requirements

Metadata Standard

- Datacite
- Dublin Core

Metadata File Format

- XML (for data collection)

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- Title
- Creator

- Publication Date
- Publication Type
- Resource identifier
- Access Rights
- Contributor (if applicable)
- Funding reference (if applicable)
- Embargo (if applicable)
- Publisher (if applicable)
- Language (if applicable)
- Description/abstract (if applicable)
- Subject (if applicable)
- File location (if applicable)

Additional Criteria/Specifications

Technical Additional Specifications

Metadata Recommended Fields

- Alternate identifier
- Related Identifier
- Format
- Source
- License Condition
- Coverage
- Ressource Version
- Citation Title
- Citation Volume
- Citation Issue
- Citation Start Page
- Citation End Page
- Citation Edition
- Citation Conference Place
- Citation Conference Date

3.2.6 OpenAlex

Open catalog of scholarly works (journal articles, conference papers, books and book chapters, datasets, and theses), authors, institutions. It includes connections between these works, finding associations through things like journals, authors, institutional affiliations, citations, concepts, and funders.

General Information

Name	OpenAlex
Website	https://openalex.org/
Owner	OurResearch
Owner type	Non-profit organization
Owner country	Canada
Launch year	2022
Scope	Any
Number of items	Over 240 million works (scholarly documents: journal, articles, conference papers, books and book chapters, datasets and theses)
Access for index users	Free
Access for index data providers	Free
Documentation	
About technical informations: https://docs.openalex.org/	
Application form for providers	
None	

Content and Service

Content type	Journal articles, conference papers, books, datasets, theses
---------------------	--

Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	articles
Full text	Link to the full text if available
Index sources	Mainly Microsoft Academic Graph and CrossRef ORCID Research Organization Registry (ROR) DOAJ Unpaywall PubMed PMC The ISSN International Centre Internet Archive Web crawls Subject-area and institutional repositories from arXiv to Zenodo and many in between
Supported standards	
Additional services	OpenAlex API (Free and no authentication needed, daily limit of API calls is 100 000 requests per user): https://docs.openalex.org/how-to-use-the-api/api-overview OpenAlex Snapshot (download and installation of a complete copy of the OpenAlex database): https://docs.openalex.org/download-all-data/openalex-snapshot
Bibliodiversity support	
No limitations on the content language	
OpenAlex provides a set of openness attributes:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● gold: Published in an OA journal that is indexed by the DOAJ. ● green: Toll-access on the publisher landing page, but there is a free copy in an OA repository. ● hybrid: Free under an open license in a toll-access journal. ● bronze: Free to read on the publisher landing page, but without any identifiable license. 	

- closed: All other articles.

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

OpenAlex automatically indexes new journals and articles. If the publications are not already stored in OpenAlex data sources. OpenAlex primarily retrieves new records from Crossref (<https://www.crossref.org/>).

Data Collection

- Automatic web crawling

Minimum Requirements

- Dependant from the data sources crawled by OpenAlex

Additional Criteria / Specifications

- Dependant from the data sources crawled by OpenAlex

3.2.7 PubMed

PubMed is a free resource supporting the search and retrieval of biomedical and life sciences literature with the aim of improving health—both globally and personally. The PubMed database contains more than 37 million citations and abstracts of biomedical literature. It does not include full text journal articles; however, links to the full text are often present when available from other sources, such as the publisher's website or PMC.

General Information

Name	PubMed
Website	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/
Owner	US National Library of Medicine (NLM)
Owner type	Public research organization
Owner country	USA
Launch year	1996

Scope	Biomedecine and health, life sciences, behavioral sciences, chemical sciences and bioengineering
Number of items	More than 37 million citations and abstracts
Access for index users	Free
Access for index data providers	Free
Documentation	
Criteria documentation: https://www.nlm.nih.gov/medline/medline_how_to_include.html	
Application form for providers	
https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/medline/publisherportal/	

Content and Service

Content type	Articles
Content language	Any
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	Journals, articles
Full text	Link to the full text when available
Index sources	Journals
Supported standards	
Main additional services	
<p>NLM Gateway (Web-based metasearch engine for many resources of the NLM): https://www.nlm.nih.gov/</p> <p>Bookshelf Free online access to books and documents in life science and healthcare): https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/</p> <p>PMC (free full-text archive of biomedical and life sciences journal literature): https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/?db=PMC</p>	

PubChem (Collection of freely accessible chemical information: chemical and physical properties, biological activities, citations and more):

<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

Biodiversity support

Website in english and mandatory english abstracts and titles, content from all countries and all languages (mainly in english) in open and restricted access

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Completion of an application form for journal suggestion after registration on the platform.

(<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/medline/publisherportal/>)

Journals must successfully pass both a Scientific Quality Review and a Technical and Indexing Requirements Check to be indexed (more informations in the criteria documentation:

https://www.nlm.nih.gov/medline/medline_how_to_include.html#scientificquality)

Data Collection

Journals and articles metadata are collected upon submission. Publishers of journals in PubMed must submit citations and abstract data electronically. PubMed only accepts citation and abstract data uploaded by SFTP in the PubMed XML tagged format described here:

https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK3828/#publisherhelp.PubMed_XML_Tagged_Format

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

Journal and Publishing History

- The journal must have been published for at least 12 month in the format that will be used for the review
- The journal must have published a minimum of 40 peer-reviewed articles (original research or review articles, clinical case reports) in final form

Publishing Policy

The journal must publish abstracts for all peer-reviewed content (minimum all peer-reviewed content in the past 12 months must contain abstracts.)

Technical Minimum Requirements

Data File Format

- XML
- SGML
- TXT
- ZIP
- TAR

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- Journal Title
- Publisher Name
- ISSN
- Volume
- Issue
- Pagination
- Publication Date
- Author List
- Author Affiliation
- Author Identifiers
- Investigators/Collaborators
- Publication Type
- DOI/ Personally Identifiable Information (PII)
- Abstract
- Conflict of Interest Statement
- ClinicalTrials.gov and other databank identifiers
- Grants/Funding information
- PubMed-ID (PMID)/DOI/PII for related articles, e.g., errata, retractions, comments

Additional Criteria / Specifications

Technical Additional Specifications

Metadata Recommended Fields

Abstract (AB) Copyright Information (CI) Affiliation (AD) Investigator Affiliation (IRAD) Article Identifier (AID) Author (AU) Author Identifier (AUID) Full Author (FAU) Book Title (BTI)

Collection Title (CTI) Comments/Corrections Conflict of Interest Statement (COIS) Corporate Author (CN) Create Date (CRDT) Date Completed (DCOM) Date Created (DA) Date Last Revised (LR) Date of Electronic Publication (DEP) Date of Publication (DP) Edition (EN) Editor and Full Editor Name (ED) and (FED) Entrez Date (EDAT) Field Abbreviation Full Personal Name as Subject (FPS) Gene Symbol (GS) General Note (GN) Grant Number (GR) Investigator Name and Full Investigator Name (IR) (FIR) ISBN (ISBN) ISSN (IS) Issue (IP) Journal Title Abbreviation (TA) Journal Title (JT) Language (LA) Location Identifier (LID) Manuscript Identifier (MID) MeSH Date (MHDA) MeSH Terms (MH) NLM Unique ID (JID) Number of References (RF) Other Abstract (OAB) Other Copyright Information (OCI) Other ID (OID) Other Term (OT) Other Term Owner (OTO) Owner (OWN) Field Abbreviation Pagination (PG) Personal Name as Subject (PS) Place of Publication (PL) Publication History Status (PHST) Publication Status (PST) Publication Type (PT) Publishing Model (PUBM) PubMed Central Identifier (PMC) PubMed Central Release (PMCR) PubMed Unique Identifier (PMID) Registry Number/EC Number (RN) Substance Name (NM) Secondary Source ID (SI) Source (SO) Space Flight Mission (SFM) Status (STAT) Subset (SB) Title (TI) Transliterated Title (TT) Volume (VI) Volume Title (VTI)

3.2.8 Scopus

Abstract and citation database which allows to search papers of peer-reviewed journals in different subject fields: life sciences, social sciences, physical sciences and health sciences. It covers three types of sources: book series, journals, and trade journals. Scopus also allows patent searches in a dedicated patent database Lexis-Nexis.

General Information

Name	Scopus
Website	https://www.scopus.com/
Owner	Elsevier
Owner type	Private company
Owner country	Netherlands
Launch year	2004
Scope	Life sciences, biomedical sciences, engineering, social sciences, arts & humanities. Low rate of research from arts, humanities and social sciences. (Jonathan Tennant, 2020)
Number of items	27 800 active journals

	94 million records
Access for index users	Subscription fee
Access for index data providers	Free
Documentation	
Content policy documentation: https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/content/content-policy-and-selection	
Application form for providers	
https://suggestor.step.scopus.com/suggestTitle/step1.cfm	

Content and Service

Content type	Journals, Articles, Books
Content language	Mainly in english (Abstract and titles in english)
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	Journals
Full text	None (restricted access)
Index sources	Journals Unpaywall (partial)
Supported standards	Unknown
Additional services	
Scopus AI (Search tool powered by generative AI): https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/scopus-ai	
Scopus Author Profiles (Output and influence of researchers and institutions): https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/author-profiles	
Scopus Metrics (CiteScore): https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/metrics#3-citescore	
Scopus API and data: https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/data#2-scopus-apis	

Bibliodiversity support

Uses of journal metrics (CiteScore).

Abstract and article titles in english. Scopus is considered to reference a low rate of “research produced in non-Western countries, non-English language research, and research from the arts, humanities, and social sciences” (Jonathan Tennant, 2020)

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Application form for journal suggestion to the Content Selection and Advisory Board (CSAB): <https://suggestor.step.scopus.com/suggestTitle/step1.cfm> and compliance with a set of editorial and technical requirements.

Data Collection Process

Journals metadata is collected upon manual submission, and the journal's records are then regularly updated through XML or PDF files retrieval.

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

Editorial Board

Journals shall have editorial boards or other governing bodies whose members are recognized experts in the subject areas included within the journal's scope. The full names and affiliations of the journal's editorial board or other governing body shall be provided on the journal's website.

Journals shall provide the full names and affiliations of the journal's editors on the journal website as well as contact information for the editorial office, including a full address.

Publishing Policy

- Be published on a regular basis
- The periodicity at which a journal publishes shall be clearly indicated.
- Peer-review content and publicly available description of the peer review process
- Have a publicly available publication ethics and publication malpractice statement

- Have content that is relevant for and readable by an international audience, meaning: have English language abstracts and titles

Copyright

The policy for copyright shall be clearly stated in the author guidelines and the copyright holder named on all published articles. Likewise, licensing information shall be clearly described in guidelines on the website, and licensing terms shall be indicated on all published articles, both HTML and PDFs.

Technical Minimum Requirements

Data File Format

- PDF
- HTML

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- ISSN (registered with the ISSN international Center)
- Journal title
- Abstract
- Subject (main)
- Journal's start year

Additional Criteria / Specifications

Editorial Additional Specifications

Journal History

- No delays or interruptions in the publication schedule

Editorial Board

- Diversity in geographical distribution of editors
- Diversity in geographical distribution of authors

Publishing Policy

- Convincing editorial policy
- Type of peer review
- Academic contribution to the field
- Clarity of abstracts
- Quality of and conformity to the stated aims and scope of the journal
- Readability of articles

- Citedness of journal articles in Scopus
- English language journal home page available

3.2.9 Web of Science

The WoS is a paid-access platform that provides access to multiple databases that provide reference and citation data from academic journals, conference proceedings and other documents in various academic disciplines.

General Information

Name	Web of Science (WoS)
Website	https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search
Owner	Clarivate
Owner type	Private company
Owner country	USA UK
Launch year	1956 with Institute for Scientific Information, 1997 with Clarivate
Scope	Life sciences, biomedical sciences, engineering, social sciences, arts & humanities.
Number of items	Above 22 000 journals
Access for index users	Subscription fee
Access for index data providers	APC
Documentation	
<p>Process and Selection Criteria: https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-discovery-and-workflow-solutions/webofscience-platform/web-of-science-core-collection/editorial-selection-process/editorial-selection-process/</p> <p>Evaluation process graph: https://clarivate.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/WoS-selection-process-Graphic_Journals_web-1.jpg</p>	

Application form for providers

<https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-publishing-solutions/publisher-portal/newusers/>

Content and Service

Content type	Journals, articles
Content language	Mainly in english (Abstract and titles in english)
Content geographical provenance	Any
Indexing level for publications	Journals
Full text	None (restricted access)
Index sources	Journals
Supported standards	Unknown
Additional services	<p>EndNote (reference management software): https://access.clarivate.com/login?app=endnote</p> <p>RefWorks (tool for citation, bibliography and reference management): https://about.proquest.com/en/products-services/refworks/</p> <p>ScholarOne (Journal Workflow Management Software): https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-publishing-solutions/scholarone/</p>
Bibliodiversity support	
<p>The evaluation includes the prestige dimension with the use of impact factor. WoS is considered to reference a low rate of "research produced in non-Western countries, non-English language research, and research from the arts, humanities, and social sciences" (Jonathan Tennant, 2020)</p>	

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Access governed by a 2-step process detailed here: <https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-publishing-solutions/publisher-portal/newusers/>

- 1st step: Creation of a user account with your institutional email address: <https://access.clarivate.com/register?app=wpp&referrer=%2Fwpp%2Fhom>
- 2nd step: Request access to the publisher portal: https://support.clarivate.com/ScientificandAcademicResearch/s/publisher-portal-access-request?language=en_US

Data Collection

Journals metadata is collected upon manual submission from the publishers. Articles metadata is regularly updated through the use of various databases.

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

Journal and Publishing History

- Timeliness or Publication Volume (the journal must state whether it has defined a publication frequency or if it operates under an irregular or continuous publication schedule)
- The journal must conform to the stated schedule)

Editorial Board

- Editorial affiliation details (Editorial Board Members must be identifiable and available for contact. Names and institutional affiliations – including country/region – of all members of the editorial team are required (such as Editor-in-Chief, Editorial Board Members, Associate Editors, Regional Editors etc.)
- Author affiliation details (Authors of all scholarly works must be accurately identified. Names and institutional affiliations – including country/region – of all contributing authors are required.)
- Editorial board composition (Editor and Editorial Board Member affiliations, geographic diversity, and publication records must be consistent with the stated scope and published content of the journal.)
- Author Distribution (The authors must have affiliations, geographic diversity, and publication records that validate their participation in the scholarly community associated with the stated scope of the journal.)

Publishing Policy

- Presence of peer review and clear statement of the peer review policy
- Scholarly content (The journal must contain primarily original scholarly material)
- Articles titles and article abstracts in english
- Bibliographic Information in Roman Script
- Clarity of language
- Presence of Ethics Statements
- Content relevance (The journal must have a well-defined scope and statement of purpose showing focus and coherence.)
- Appropriate Citations to the literature (It is expected that articles will appropriately acknowledge the surrounding literature for the topic.)

Technical Minimum Requirements

Metadata Mandatory Fields

- ISSN
- Journal title
- Journal publisher
- Abstract

Additional Criteria/Specifications

Editorial Additional Specifications

Editorial Board

- Author Citation Analysis (Most authors should have a discernible publication history in the WoS.)
- Editorial Board Citation Analysis (Most Editorial Board Members should have a discernible publication history in the WoS.)

Publishing Policy

- Comparative Citation Analysis (Our most selective indices (Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) and Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI)) contain the most impactful journals in their discipline.)
- Content Significance (The content in the journal should be of interest, importance, and value to its intended readership and to WoS subscribers)

4 CONCLUSION

The documentation presented in this report represents a prototype which will be refined and finalized before distribution to the public. The documentation will indeed be integrated with the living handbook prepared within WP7, and the specific requirements and possibilities related to the handbook still have to be decided at this stage. The KB itself should also be made public, either alongside the documentation or connected to it, depending on the living handbook specifications. In addition, and before their integration in the living handbook, the documentation and KB prototypes will be presented to the community in public events in the coming months in order to fine-tune them.

From the reflections made and the methods applied, it appears that some main characteristics of the indexes emerge, although an exhaustive classification universally applicable may still not be possible. There are two main reasons for this impossibility. First, the indexes can have characteristics that belong to more than one category. Second, the classification itself may not correspond to the practices and understanding of each and every user. Precisely, however, the classification effort has a particular importance in terms of usage for our specific project. While the description of each service through the documentation and the filtering features proposed through the Typology table both facilitate the understanding of individual services, a classification, even approximative, with broader categories would bring a useful clarification of the landscape. Furthermore, some important distinctions can also have an impact in the building of the DDH. Indeed, as the DDH will collect and expose data, the data collection process of the indexes has obviously an impact on how OADJs data will be able to appear on the DDH.

From this point of view, the data collection process can result in a classification useful both for OADJs and the DDH. It is indeed possible to make a distinction between those types of data collection:

- Web crawling (GScholar, OpenAlex)
- Harvesting data exposed via OAI repositories (OpenAIRE, BASE, GoTriple)
- Data pushed to indexes via API (DOAJ, Crossref, PubMed) or manual submission (via SFTP or webform).

Another important distinction, both for the OADJs and the DDH, is the evaluation perimeter, as it is reported already in the Typology table. The fact that the evaluation considers only technical aspects, or also editorial ones, corresponds to a major classification dichotomy, that has, besides the interest of a clarification of the landscape, a direct impact on the classification usage: OADJs and the DDH may discard one of these types for feasibility or policy reasons.

Such a preliminary analysis will be further detailed in the second version of the report, once the KB and the related index documentation will be enriched and stabilized. In this further stage, broad classifications like the ones mentioned above will help OADJs to select the appropriate index for their title. In relation to this work, it is also planned to provide the KB in a more reusable and actionable format, which will facilitate its publication, on one hand, but also, on the other, potentially allow for automated processing and comparison.

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All references and websites mentioned in the document were last checked for availability on 02.07.2024.

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CRAFT-OA Consortium (2022). *CRAFT-OA Proposal*. Proposal number: 101094397. Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01. Topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-02. Submitted 20.04.2022.

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5.2 List of Websites

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<https://access.clarivate.com/login?app=endnote>

<https://access.clarivate.com/register?app=wpp&referrer=%2Fwpp%2Fhom>

<https://api.gotriple.eu/>

<https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker/overview>

<https://clarivate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-discovery-and-workflow-solutions/webofscience-platform/>

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<https://journalcheckertool.org/>
<https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/erihplus/>
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<https://openalex.org/>
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<https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/inclusion.html#indexing>
<https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/metrics.html>
<https://suggestor.step.scopus.com/suggestTitle/step1.cfm>
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<https://theplace.discourse.group/>
<https://thepund.it/>
<https://thinkchecksubmit.org/>
<https://usagecounts.openaire.eu/>
<https://www.base-search.net/>
<https://www.centre-mersenne.org/en/>
<https://www.crossref.org/>
<https://www.dimensions.ai/>
<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/author-profiles>
<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/content/content-policy-and-selection>
<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/data#2-scopus-apis>
<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/metrics#3-citescore>
<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/scopus-ai>

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https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK3828/#publisherhelp.PubMed_XML_Tagged_Format
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/medline/publisherportal/>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/?db=PMC>
<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/>
https://www.nlm.nih.gov/medline/medline_how_to_include.html
https://www.nlm.nih.gov/medline/medline_how_to_include.html#scientificquality
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<https://www.scopus.com/>
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<https://www.semantics.gr/authorities/vocabularies/SSH-LCSH/?language=en>
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/>
<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search>
<https://zenodo.org/>

APPROVAL PENDING

6 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Indexes typology criteria21

APPROVAL PENDING

7 ANNEXES

7.1 Knowledge Base current version

Administration	Name		
	Country		
	Owner		
	Owner type		
	Access		
	Website		
	Launch year		
	Nb of items		
Service provision	Service type		
	Service description		
	Documentation: general		
	Documentation: technical		
	Support		
Joining options			
Criteria for publications	Target provider		
	Publication level		
	Requirements	Editorial	
		Content language	
		Format	
		Metadata: minimum	
		Metadata: recommended	
Metadata: optimum			

		Other
	SEO	
Data management	Data collection process	
	Data sources	
	Data collected	
	Standards used	
Related services		
Biodiversity		
Wikipedia		

APPROVAL PENDING

7.2 KB Example: DOAJ

Administration	Name	DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals)
	Country	UK/Denmark
	Owner	Infrastructure Services for Open Access
	Owner type	Non-profit organisation / community interest company (Infrastructure Services for Open Access C.I.C.)
	Access for index users	Free
	Access for index data providers	Free upon registration
	Website	https://doaj.org/
	Launch year	2003
	Number of indexed items	Above 20 000 Journals, Above 10 million Articles
	Scope	Any
Service provision	Service type	Directory of OA journals and articles
	Service description	Community-curated list of peer-reviewed OA journals, maintained by IS4OA. DOAJ also allows for article metadata collection and display, and free distribution of journal and article metadata.
	Documentation: general	About DOAJ: https://doaj.org/about/ About application: https://doaj.org/apply/guide/
	Documentation: technical	Metadata upload: https://doaj.org/docs/faq/ XML metadata upload: https://doaj.org/docs/xml/ API metadata download: https://doaj.org/api/v3/docs OAI-PMH metadata download: https://doaj.org/docs/oai-pmh/

	Support	Rich online documentation Reviewers reports
	Content geographical provenance	134 countries represented
	Full text	link to the full text available
Joining options		For publishers: compliance with set of editorial and technical requirements
Criteria for publications	Target provider	Publishers (OA)
	Indexing level for publications	Journal
	Requirements	<p>OA journals OA statement Open licensing Free text available with no embargo</p> <p>Any research subject area Publish at least five research articles per year Primary target audience of researchers or practitioners</p> <p>New or flipped journal must demonstrate a publishing history of more than one year or have published at least ten OA research articles.</p>
	Content language	any
	Data file format	HTML or PDF
	Metadata file format	XML, JSON, Webform (text)
	Metadata standard	
	Metadata: minimum	Journal title ISSN e-ISSN

		Metadata: recommended	
		Metadata: optimum	
		Other	
	SEO/UX	<p>Journals with own URL and homepage Articles as independent full text document Intrusive advertising Consistency of translation if multilingual website</p> <p>Easily visible information required on the website: OA policy Aims and scope Editorial board (including institutional affiliations of all members) Instructions for authors Editorial process (peer review) Licensing terms Copyright terms Author charges Contact details</p>	
Data management	Data collection process	<p>Journals metadata: upon submission</p> <p>Articles metadata: upon submission DOAJ API DOAJ or Crossref XML Webform</p>	
	Index sources	Journals	
	Data collected	Metadata	
	Supported standard	Dublin Core, DOAJ XML schema, Crossref XML schema	

Related services	https://doaj.org/preservation/ https://doaj.org/apply/transparency/ https://thinkchecksubmit.org/ https://theplace.discourse.group/ https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/
Bibliodiversity	World-wide coverage of countries and languages Gold and Diamond OA.
Wikipedia	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Directory_of_Open_Access_Journals

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7.3 KB Example: Google Scholar

Administration	Name	Google Scholar
	Country	USA
	Owner	Google
	Owner type	Private company
	Access for index users	Free
	Access for index data proviers	Free
	Launch year	2004
	Website	https://scholar.google.com/
	Number of indexed items	Above 100 million scholarly documents (Madian Khabsa, C. Lee Giles, 2014)
	Scope	Any
Service provision	Service type	Searchable bibliographic index
	Service description	A freely accessible web search engine that indexes the full text or metadata of scholarly literature across an array of publishing formats and disciplines. (Quoted from Wikipedia)
	Documentation: general	https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/incusion.html#overview
	Documentation: technical	https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/incusion.html#indexing
	Support	Online documentation
	Content geographical provenance	Any
	Full text	link to the full text when available
Joining options		Automated crawling
Criteria for	Target provider	Webmasters / Publishers / Authors

publications	Indexing level for publications		Article/Paper
	Requirements	Editorial	Either full text or abstract freely available (no sign-in, no specific software to use, no popups, etc.)
		Content type	Scholarly articles only. Journal papers, conference papers, technical reports, or their drafts, dissertations, pre-prints, post-prints, or abstracts. Content such as news or magazine articles, book reviews, and editorials is not appropriate for Google Scholar.
		Content language	Any language
		Data file format	PDF or HTML one separate file for each paper (either PDF or HTML file)
		Metadata file format	n/a
		Metadata standard	HTML metatags supporting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highwire Press tags ● BE Press tags ● PRISM tags ● Dublin Core tags
		Metadata : minimum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PDF: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Title (large font) ○ Authors (below title) ○ Bibliographic citation of the paper (in first page footer) ● Bibliography (separate section)HTML (metadata included in metatags of the HTML file): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Title ○ Authors

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Publication date ○ Bibliographic citation of the paper ○ Bibliography
		Metadata : recommended	n/a
		Metadata : optimum	n/a
		Other	
	SEO		<p>Depending on the number of papers on the website:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● if small amount: all articles should be listed on 1 page ● if thousands: the website should contain full list of all articles ordered by publication or entry date ● if more than 100 000: specific browsing interface with the last updates <p>If robots.txt is used, the file should be configured to allow GScholar robots crawling</p>
Data management	Data collection process		web crawling (robots)
	Index sources		any website containing scholarly articles with proper URL
	Data collected		metadata about articles and/or PDF if available

	Supported standard	HTML metatags supporting: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highwire Press tags ● BE Press tags ● PRISM tags ● Dublin Core tags
Related services		<p>Google scholar Metrics (visibility and influence of recent articles in scholarly publications): https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/metrics.html</p> <p>Google scholar Profiles (showcase of authors publications): https://scholar.google.com/intl/fr/scholar/citations.html</p>
Bibliodiversity		No limitations on the language of the content, or the publishing business model
Wikipedia		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Google_Scholar

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7.4 Index Documentation Template

(Service description)

General Information

Name	
Website	
Owner	
Owner type	
Owner country	
Launch year	
Scope	
Number of items	
Access for index users	
Access for index data providers	
Documentation	
Application form for providers	

Content and Service

Content type	
Content language	
Content geographical provenance	
Indexing level for publications	
Full text	

Index sources	
Supported standards	
Additional services	
Bibliodiversity support	

Requirements for Academic Publications

Joining Process

Data Collection

Minimum Requirements

Editorial Minimum Requirements

Journal and Publishing History

Editorial Board

Publishing Policy

Copyright

Technical Minimum Requirements

Metadata Standard

Data File Format

Metadata File Format

Metadata Mandatory Fields

Additional Criteria/Specifications

(Same subcategories as minimum requirements)

Editorial Additional Specifications

Technical Additional Specifications

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